

THE ROLE OF SOCIAL AND HUMANITARIAN SCIENCES IN FORMING THE SPIRITUAL IMAGE OF YOUTH

Egamberdiyev Javlonbek

International innovation university (Karshi, Uzbekistan)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10775003>

Annotation: In this article, issues such as teaching social and humanitarian sciences in educational institutions in order to form the ideas of preserving national independence in young people, their independent thinking, expressing a rational attitude to the ongoing processes, and drawing correct conclusions are studied. .

Key words: ideas of preserving independence, nationality, human, educational processes, spiritual culture, self-awareness, social and humanitarian sciences.

Enter. expanding teaching of social and humanitarian sciences in all educational institutions is the necessity of today. Expanding the teaching of social and humanitarian sciences in educational institutions: firstly, pupils and students develop the ability to independently think and make independent conclusions in relation to the events taking place in society; secondly, expanding the teaching of social and humanitarian sciences will greatly contribute to the effective progress of propaganda; thirdly, the political and legal culture of young people increases; fourthly, new management leaders will emerge from among the youth.

Analysis and results. The development of society shows its development characteristics based on the achievements of science. As the society is developing, there is a proportional increase in various threats against it. The 21st century has led to an increase in the scope of such pressures. Developing countries are taking measures to protect their citizens from external and internal pressure. The task of implementing complex measures to form citizens' ideas of preserving independence is becoming a priority. In particular, ensuring that young people do not fall under the influence of harmful ideas by forming their ideological immunity has risen to the level of state policy. More than 60 percent of the population of our country are young people. The influence of young people in state activities is increasing day by day. Youth has become the main driving force of the state. For this reason, forming young people as spiritually mature individuals is an urgent task of today. Because the activity among young people is much higher than other strata of the population. The feeling of being affected, mobility, reactionary thinking, abandoning the previous

ones, striving for a new world is extremely high among young people. Taking into account these feelings, the forces of spiritual and ideological influence aim to use the youth and expand their ranks. He tries to fill the spiritual void in the youth with false ideas. Even if it has a little influence, soon it will take over the mind and heart of the youth and turn it against their country. Today's ideological pressures plan to realize their malicious goals by turning one nation's representative against his own blood rather than another. At the beginning of the new millennium, the process of such influence became a global plague of the century. Types of spiritual and ideological pressures have taken root, the threat has become international and branching from nationalism. In these currents, educating young people on the basis of the ideas of preserving independence is gaining urgent importance. Therefore, a separate analysis of the scientific-theoretical foundations and practical possibilities of the formation of ideological immunity among young people is on the agenda. Specialists in the field have defined various subjective ways of educating young people based on the ideas of preserving independence. In the course of our research, we will pay special attention to the unique way of educating young people based on the ideas of preserving independence, increasing the hours of study of social and humanitarian sciences in educational institutions and forming immunity through the influence of education in it.

Education in the conditions of independence, independent thinking is an important factor in forming the ability, active attitude to the world, qualification of every young person. In order for young people to think independently, express a rational attitude to the ongoing processes, and draw the right conclusions, organize the teaching of social and humanitarian sciences in educational institutions based on the requirements of the time, and achieve effective results by increasing the number of study hours. provision is becoming a necessity. The important task in this regard is that every citizen, every person must determine his duty and responsibility for the development of society and its renewal, protecting our spiritual life from various threats and attacks on this basis. If we think more deeply about this issue, a clear idea about the unique social structure of the society based on these principles, its image, ways of development, and priority features can only be obtained through different opinions and debates. it is necessary to admit that it is obvious and to take it as a criterion for ourselves. The role of social sciences is extremely unique for the development of the human self. In the educational process, it provides information about the nature, purpose, goals, tasks, and scope of the various

threats that are happening in the society through social sciences. Not to fall under their influence, scientifically substantiates protective measures. Extensive propaganda work is carried out during the education process for the young people who are studying.

Subjects are branched through classification and the quality of education gradually increases based on their characteristics. Textbooks in schools are directed based on the distribution of classes, taking into account the age of students. The child begins to acquire the necessary skills in the educational process appropriate for his age. "Etiquette" lessons were held in elementary grades. It provides primary education on family, neighborhood, homeland, nationality, human qualities, the first directions of insecurity, community, charity, honesty, honesty, bravery, courage, the support of the homeland, the heritage of ancestors, and reading. Children acquire knowledge and skills about the first buds of humanity. Human qualities are awakened in the heart of a young child. Stories, proverbs, narratives, poems, proverbs, epics, legends taught in science lead children to goodness. Pleasant, graceful, noble qualities of hope for the future are awakened in them. The subject "Etiquette" was taught from the first to the fourth grade in a simple and meaningful form. Starting from the 2020-2021 academic year, the subject of "Etiquette" has been included in the subject of "Education" in schools. However, the topics of "Etiquette" within the subject "Education", the subject hour, and the form of education continue as they are. Only, the name of the science has changed. It is not wrong to say that this subject provides enough knowledge for elementary school students. Because the basic information of the formation of immunity in a young student is taught based on specific details and serves to instill in them feelings of pride towards the Motherland and the dream of contributing to the development of the state.

However, the provision of specialists in the subject of "Education" taught in general education schools is not properly implemented. There are some objections to the teaching system of this subject. In fact, schools in all regions of Uzbekistan have different approaches to the question of which specialists should teach "Education". In most schools, the subject of "Education" is taught by "historian" and "primary education" specialists. There is a shortage of specialists in "national idea, moral foundations and legal education" in many schools. The process of attracting and distributing them to all general education schools is in an unsatisfactory state. The role of history is extremely important in strengthening the ideas of preserving independence among students. In general education schools, history is distributed according to the norm. However,

teaching the subject of "Education" by historians or primary education specialists is somewhat inappropriate for educational purposes. But how long will we continue to pretend that there is an artificial lack of specialists. In the curriculum of the 2022-2023 academic year, the direction "National idea, foundations of spirituality and legal education" in higher educational institutions in the field of pedagogy, "Theory and history of the state and law", "Social life and religion", "History and theory of ideas", "Spiritual foundations of the fight against extremism and terrorism", "Philosophy", "Information of society and ideological immunity", "Constitutional law", "Ethics", "Ma "Administrative Law", "Civil Law", "Spirituality", "Labor Law", "Ethics", "Oratory Art", "Systematic Analysis of Ideological Processes", "Globalization and Ideological-Ideological Threats", "Family Law", "Ethnoculture", "National Idea and Interethnic Relations", "Methodology of Teaching Educational Sciences", "Methodology of Teaching Legal Sciences", "Financial Law", "Social Philosophy", "Procedural Law", "Fundamentals of Legal Culture and Legal Education", "Fundamentals of Geopolitics", "Technologies of Propagation of the National Idea", "Management Ethics", "Criminal Law", "History of World Political-Ideological Doctrines", "Ma "Methodology of organization of spiritual and educational work", "Ecological law" and other specialized subjects are taught. In the areas of history, the subject "Methodology of teaching educational subjects" and "Moral foundations of the fight against extremism and terrorism" can be taught. Other specialty subjects related to "Education" are not taught. The same is true for primary education. Now a legitimate question arises. Which specialists are more interested in "education"? Is it right to put the burden on historians and primary education specialists, saying that there is no expert? It has been 23 years since the establishment of the specialization "National idea, foundations of spirituality and legal education" in our country. Is it difficult to provide general education schools with these specialists? Why then, there are more contingents of "History" courses than "National idea, spiritual foundations and legal education" courses in pedagogical institutes? We know that you can get clear answers to questions through your own conclusions.

Social and humanitarian sciences taught in general education schools and institutions of higher education play an incomparable role in the formation of ideas of preserving independence in young people. It is necessary to expand the teaching of these subjects in higher education institutions. From the first years of independence, among the social sciences in the first block of higher education institutions are "History of Uzbekistan", "Philosophy", "Ethics", "Aesthetics",

"Foundations of spirituality and religious studies", "Cultural studies", "Political studies"., such subjects as "Civil Society" have been taught. Starting from 2018, only one subject "Philosophy" is being taught in higher education institutions, in addition to the subject "Newest History of Uzbekistan". It has only 60 hours. The rest of the subjects were absorbed into the "Philosophy" subject. According to the opinion of many experts in the field, the sharp reduction of social and humanitarian sciences will increase irreparable problems in the future. In the processes observed in the nations of the world, dehumanization by possessing the human mind and heart is showing its effect today. The influence of social sciences in the formation of ideological immunity of young people and its improvement was noticeable. Even today, the need for social and humanitarian sciences is already felt. Our youth are easily deceived by groups that promote various foreign ideas. Because some of our young people have not studied social sciences thoroughly. That's why they are more likely to be followed. Our great ancestors taught the world with their scientific and creative discoveries. He did not follow others, but followed others after himself. We must be a people with the power to follow, not to follow. Otherwise, we will leave the path of development and sink into the mire of decline again. We easily lose the achievements of our ancestors [3, B.151].

Expanding the teaching of social and humanitarian sciences among our youth ensures effective results in the following tasks:

First of all, a thorough understanding of the essence of the national idea and spirituality requires a sense of civic responsibility and duty, trust and faith in the Motherland. Only then will it perform an important task that can serve to unite and develop the people and the nation.

Secondly, today's globalization process increases the need to expand social sciences that embody the essence of spirituality and the national idea in the past, now and in the future. That is why, no matter how much this world follows the laws of enlightened development, the effort and attempt to change the human heart, mind, faith, and belief will always be preserved.

Thirdly, the sphere of ideas and ideology, which is the composition of social and humanitarian sciences, is related to the system of trust and faith, worldview, and interests. That is why we cannot agree with those who say that social and humanitarian sciences should be reduced. For example, with the creation of an ideological gap in a person's mind and thinking, the ideas of independence and dependence begin to take precedence over independent thought in his

worldview. Therefore, it becomes necessary to teach more social and humanitarian sciences.

Fourthly, the topics of social and humanitarian sciences encourage people to live in harmony with the world, not to live apart from the world, to keep themselves in their own shell. It teaches to look at it with respect, relying only on national spiritual values and heritage, and not to break away from it, relying on one's own national spiritual foundations.

Fifth, studying the sciences related to the national idea and spirituality instills national pride in a person and encourages him to live knowing his identity. The sciences that embody the foundations of spirituality and the national idea are different from other social and humanitarian sciences, and progress in enriching the identity of the Motherland, the nation, while keeping it always in the heart, keeping the pain, dreams, goals, and honor high. serves as a factor [4, B.384-386]

Sixth, changes in the world demand new tasks for these sciences, education of young people in the spirit of loyalty to the Motherland. That's why paying special attention to social and humanitarian sciences in the educational system, studying it in harmony with the life of an individual and society, in connection with noble goals, will bear fruit.

CONCLUSION

1) Today's globalization process increases the need to expand social sciences that embody the essence of spirituality and the national idea in the past, now and in the future. That is why, no matter how much this world follows the laws of enlightened development, the effort and attempt to change the human heart, mind, faith, and belief will always be preserved.

2) The sphere of ideas and ideology, which is the composition of social and humanitarian sciences, is related to the system of trust and faith, worldview, and interests. That is why we cannot agree with those who say that social and humanitarian sciences should be reduced. For example, with the creation of an ideological gap in a person's mind and thinking, the ideas of independence and dependence begin to take precedence over independent thought in his worldview. Therefore, it becomes necessary to teach more social and humanitarian sciences.

3) Expanding the teaching of social and humanitarian sciences in educational institutions: firstly, pupils and students develop an independent opinion and the ability to make independent conclusions regarding the events taking place in society; secondly, expanding the teaching of social and humanitarian sciences

will greatly contribute to the effective progress of propaganda; thirdly, the political and legal culture of young people increases; fourthly, new management leaders will emerge from among the youth.

List of references:

1. Egamberdiyev, J. (2024). SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL BASES OF ORGANIZING SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL WORK IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN THE CONDITIONS OF GLOBALIZATION. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(3), 209-214.
2. Javlonbek, E. (2023). SOCIO-HISTORICAL GENESIS OF IDEAS THAT FORM THE SPIRITUAL IMAGE OF YOUTH. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 426-432.
3. Жабборов, А. М., & Жабборов, Ж. А. (2016). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ЗНАЧИМОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ УЗБЕКСКИХ НАРОДНЫХ ПОСЛОВИЦ ПРИ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИИ УЧЕБНО-ВОСПИТАТЕЛЬНОГО ПРОЦЕССА. Журнал научных публикаций аспирантов и докторантов, (3), 93-95.
4. Жабборов Ж.А. Маънавий эҳтиёжлар – жамият тараққиётининг мезони // «Трансформація суспільних наук: соціально-економічний, лінгвістичний, політичний та іт-виміри» ІІ Міжнародна наукова конференція. 22.10.2021. Харків, UKR. 40-43 бет. <https://doi.org/10.36074/mcnd-22.10.2021>
5. Жабборов Ж.А. Ўзбекистонда таълим-тарбия тизимини объектив заруратга мослаштириш бўйича олиб борилаётган давлат сиёсати. BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. (6), 2021 y. 19-28 b.
6. Жабборов Ж.А. Илм-фанда эҳтиёжлар таснифи. Збірник наукових праць Л'ОГОΣ. 2021. <https://doi.org/10.36074/logos-29.10.2021.v1.34>
7. Жабборов Ж.А. Постмодерн жамият зиддиятларининг маънавий эҳтиёжлар юксалишига таъсири (фалсафий таҳлил). Традиційні та інноваційні підходи до наукових досліджень, 149.
8. Жабборов Ж.А. Мамлакатимиз олимларининг илмий тадқиқотларида маънавий эҳтиёжлар муаммосининг талқини // Жамият ва инновациялар – Общество и инновации – Society and innovations Special Issue – 5 (2021) / ISSN 2181-1415. Impact Factor: SJIF 2021 = 5.395. Б. 484-491.
9. Jabborov J.A. Analysis of spiritual needs. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary ..., 2021.

10. Azimovich J. J. MA'NAVIY ENTIYOJLAR RIVOJLANISHINING IJTIMOYIY-MADANIY OMILLARI //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 30-35.
11. Жабборов Ж.А. Эҳтиёжлар тизимида - маънавий эҳтиёжлар. Актуальные вызовы современной науки. II Международная научная конференция. 2017. С 62-64.
12. Жабборов Ж. А. Ғарб олимларининг илмий тадқиқотларида эҳтиёжлар тизимининг таҳлили //Ўзбекистон миллий ахборот агентлиги-ЎЗА илм-фан бўлими (электрон журнал). – 2021. – С. 316-325.
13. Жабборов Ж.А. Маънавий эҳтиёжлар-жамият тараққиётининг мезони. Материали конференцій I Міжнародна наукова конференція «Трансформація суспільних наук: соціально-економічний, лінгвістичний, політичний». Украина. 2021.
14. Jabbarov J. A 2023. INTERPRETATION OF NEEDS IN THE SPIRITUAL HERITAGE OF OUR ANCESTORS. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development. (Dec. 2023), 633–636.
15. Jabbarov J. A. INTERPRETATION OF NEEDS IN THE SPIRITUAL HERITAGE OF OUR ANCESTORS.
16. Jabbarov J.A. Society in his Life Spiritual of Needs Held Place. merican Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769), 2(1), 48–51.
17. Жабборов, Ж.А. (2021). Интерпретация проблемы духовных потребностей в научных исследованиях ученых нашей страны. Общество и инновации, 2(5/S), 484–491. <https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-1415-vol2-iss5/S-pp484-491>
18. Жабборов, А. М., Жабборов, И. А., & Жабборов, Ж. А. (2015). ЭТНИЧЕСКИЕ СТЕРЕОТИПЫ И ПСИХОЛОГИЯ САМОБЫТНОСТИ УЗБЕКСКОГО НАРОДА. Журнал научных публикаций аспирантов и докторантов, (1), 80-83.
19. Jabbarov, J. A. "INTERPRETATION OF NEEDS IN THE SPIRITUAL HERITAGE OF OUR ANCESTORS."
20. Жабборов Ж. А. АЖДОДЛАРИМИЗ МАЪНАВИЙ МЕРОСИДА ЭҲТИЁЖЛАР ТАЛҚИНИ //УЧИНЧИ УЙҒОНИШ ҒОЯЛАРИНИНГ ИЛМ-ФАН ТАРАҚҚИЁТИДАГИ ЎРНИ.

